

Smart Waste Management Application for Pet Bottle Compactor

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Abstract

Millions polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottles are produced every day and get in landfills, rivers, seas and oceans. PETs lasts 700-800 years until they begin to decompose and will only disintegrate after about 1000 years. Although very difficult to disintegrate, PET is a 100% recyclable material. PET / recycled polyester is used as raw material for textile fibres or other PET packaging. Recycling is a solution both to reduce environmental pollution and to save natural resources. Recycling and selective waste collection is a major issue worldwide for which innovative technical solutions are sought. This paper presents the results of experimental research for an intelligent waste management system, conducted by a team of researchers in the frame of master's program Complex Projects' Engineering and Management from University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest. The customized macroplanning for the developed technical solutions with multiple design phases, was based on business strategy, needs analysis, concept generation and selection eventually ending up with the building and testing of a functional prototype. Also, based on a customized electrical and software architecture, a Smart Management Application for controlling the prototype is described in this work.

Keywords: Industry 4.0., New Product Development, Project-Based Pedagogy, Smart Management Application, Waste Compactor.

Introduction

The European Union aims to make all plastic packaging recyclable by 2030. Under current European legislation, all countries are required to recycle a certain percentage of the amount of waste from PET packaging. However, Romania recycles an insignificant amount of the entire volume of waste it produces, the rest being thrown in the landfill.

Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) packaging can be recycled and used for the manufacture of new containers or for raw materials in the textile industry. The diversity of types of packaging and the materials from which they are made complicates the recycling process. The recycling process sometimes becomes difficult and expensive. The quality and price of the recycled product compared to the original plastic is also a problem that complicates the recycling process.

A team of researchers from master program Complex Projects' Engineering and Management from University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest works to design and develop an innovative compactor system with selective waste collection controlled through a Smart Management Application developed in LabVIEW as a virtual instrument.

This paper is based on a master team research coordination regarding an initiative to empower and educate the public about the importance of recycling, providing effective means for selective waste collection with minimal user effort. This idea was generated in the frame of the master program Complex Projects' Engineering and Management from University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest. A key component of learning strategy is Project-Based Pedagogy (PBP) for a new product development according to ABAZA B. et al. (2015).

During last two academic years two master teams chosen to develop different innovative technical solutions for home use systems dedicated for compacting recyclable containers, designed with

selective waste collection capability thus facilitating the recycling process. The development process included building and testing functional prototypes based on which the optimization of technical solution was made.

Initially student’s research was focused on development of mechanical system architecture designing different technical solutions for compacting the waste and for selective waste collection. This paper investigates and propose solutions for the electrical architecture and for the software component which should be designed as a Smart Waste Management Application dedicated to be compatible with all these mechanical concepts but also to integrate Industry 4.0 concepts and principles.

Macroplanning

Based on customized macroplanning for new product development and PBP teams developed technical solutions which have gone through multiple design phases, while having continuous improvements made based on: business strategy, needs analysis, concept generation and selection eventually ending up with the building and testing of a functional prototype. Figure 1 explains the macroplanning defined according with academic program. This is another key element to take in account which influenced teaching activities and project development from the perspective of PBP integration, as Abaza mentioned (2020).

Fig 1. Macroplanning

Preliminary experimental trials

To determine the forces required to compress the waste, a series of preliminary experimental determinations were made using a large variety of types of waste: cans, PET bottles, Tetra Pack, of different heights and thicknesses. It was used a Zwick/Roell ProLine table-top testing machine (Figure 2).

The results of the experimental determinations are presented in table 1.

Figure 3 shows the forces – deformation diagram during the experimental research, where:

- F1 – is the force required to initiate compression.
- F2 - the force at which the compression is performed.
- F3 - the maximum force it reaches at the end of the deformation.

Fig 2. Zwick/Roell ProLine testing machine

Table 1. Experimental results

Waste Type	Material	Compression Ratio	H waste [mm]	v [mm/min]	F1 [N]	F2 [N]	F3 [N]
Can	Al	1/5	150	600	540	110	545
Can	Al	1/5	120	480	460	110	755
Bottle	Pet	1/4	330	1000	220	120	229
Bottle	Pet	1/5	355	1000	140	90	348
Bottle	Pet	1/5	350	1000	290	100	290
Tetra Pack	Paper	1/4	250	1000	100	150	170

Fig 3. Force – deformation diagram

On the x-axis is deformation nominal D of the waste (bottle/can/tetra pack) in millimetres from start point until the point where the deformation was completed. On the y-axis is variance of force F in N during the deformation of the waste.

All experimental trials showed that during the deformation process there are 3 main forces thresholds to take in account: F_1 , F_2 and F_3 . F_1 is the spike of the force when initiating the deformation, F_2 is the force during the deformation after F_1 and F_3 is the force at the end of deformation when there is no more volume reduction to be made. Based on this force variance the compactor should provide the F_1 and F_2 and to stop deformation just before F_3 . In this case the most relevant are the highest values for the force F_1 required to initiate the deformation process. Based on the F_1 values from all waste tested it results that the most disadvantaged case to be cover it is the case of the deformation of can where the force F_1 it is about 600N. This is an important design input to take in account in the next design phases.

All experiments showed that stability of the waste is very important during deformation process and in any concept design of the compactor should provide solution for proper guidance and orientation of the waste.

Concept generation

Based on these preliminary experiments the development process of the compactor followed all design phases according with macroplanning from figure 1.

Below in figure 4 is a selection of 2 design concepts for the compactor (Sevastian, 2019). The teams generate more versions but most of them used a screw nut mechanism for the compression subsystem of the waste. The screw is driven by an DC electric motor. Each concept proposes different solutions for compressing active parts taking in account the preliminary experimental trials.

Fig 4. Concept design

The global design of the compactor (Figure 5) took in account the home use integration together with all main integrated functions: reducing the volume and selective waste collection.

Fig 5. Global design (Sevastian, 2019)

Development of Smart Management Application

Based on high accelerated development of Based on these preliminary experiments the development process of the compactor followed all design phases according with macroplanning from figure 4 (Sevastian, 2019)

Waste management domain is also affected by the high accelerated digital transformation proposed by Industry 4.0. A lot of research effort was focused on defining effective smart city concepts which integrate also wate management solutions. Basically, smart management applications use sensors to measure fill levels from waste container (bins) and generate different kind of notifications for assisting decision when to empty those bins and to collect the waste in an effective way. Many solutions where studied and developed using different kind of modern technologies like Cloud-based smart waste management (Aazam 2016) or Smart Waste Collection Monitoring and Alert System via IoT (Hisham Che Soh 2019).

This paper proposes a different development approach for the whole waste management ecosystem based on Industry 4.0 concepts and principles where the is a vertical integration with a hierarchical level component. It is about the integration of all IT system components at various hierarchical levels into one comprehensive solution. In our case these hierarchical levels are respectively the field level, the control level, the process line level, the operations level and the ecosystem planning level represented by the Waste Management Ecosystem (Figure 6).

Fig 6. Waste Management Architecture

From this perspective our system will have similar levels like those from an automation pyramid:

1. Level one: sensors and actuators – connecting what should be connected at the level of compactor physical active parts representing the ‘things and device’ layer)
2. Level two: systems and internal services – monitor and manage in real time process at the level of the controller
3. Level three: connectivity – connect for new applications and capabilities of the compactor
4. Level four: new services and ecosystems – transformation from the Waste Management Ecosystem.

Smart Waste Management and Execution Application plays a central role in development of the first stages of this approach based on Industry 4.0 transformation representing the digital hub of information and connectivity. In our case this will be represented by a virtual instrument software developed in LabVIEW able to cover all main roles and capabilities relates to:

- Remote control.
- Remote Diagnosis.
- Conditioning Monitoring.
- Systems Health Monitoring.

Smart Waste Management and Execution Application

Designing the Smart Waste Management and Execution Application was made based mechanical architecture of the compactors and based on electrical system architecture presented in the figure 7. Basically, this architecture describes the main components from level 1 and the way how these are interacting with components from level 2 from the automation pyramid.

Fig 7. Electrical System Architecture

According to this figure, the software development should take in account interaction between main components from the level 1 with components from level 2 of the automation pyramid.

The components belonging to the level 1 in our case are:

- Limit switches which give the feedback about the position of the active compression plate.
- Active compression plate driven by screw nut mechanism. The 12V DC electrical motor will rotate the screw according with the compacting parameters given by the controller state machine

through the motor driver connected between them. The nut will slide the active compression plate for producing the compression or for homing (repositioning to the home position).

- Confirm, Select and Abort buttons which allow to the user to select and interact with the compactor.
- 12V Power supply with power switch.
- Display connected to the controller. A local display is necessary even that the software may will have different remote interfaces on different devices.
- Safety devices like buzzer (generation of different audio signals), E-STOP button for stopping the compactor in any moment.

The main components belonging to the level 2 in our case are:

- Controller – in our case it was used and Aduino Mega 2560.
- WiFi Module type ESP8266 used for wifi communication.
- SD Card Module used for local logging data to the micro SD card.

Programming the Controller State Machines

Based on functional analysis and previous electrical architecture there were defined 8 states machines for the controller:

- **DEBUG_STATE // 0** (System start-up and check all connected devices). In this state the system when is power up will check the status of all connected devices and will define the start-up states for all components. Figure 8 shows the interface for debug state when it can be seen that system by default will pass through automatically or, if necessary, it can be active the manual mode when a series of settings can be made for setting up the compactor: serial port selection (if wired connection is necessary), setup a new home position.

Fig 8. The interface for Debug State

- PET_STATE (Figure 9) // 1 (Compactor plate moves with to the left for compacting a pet). In this state the system will compact a PET moving the active plate, which generate the compression of PET, with a specific speed until the desired deformation is obtained. The speed is tuned using dedicated proportional–integral–derivative controller parameters (PID) for producing the proper speed of compressing plate to obtain deformation to a desired volume ratio compression. These parameters were defined based on experimental trials of the prototype for PET waste according with the combination of DC motor type, motor driver and mechanical components from the screw nut mechanism.

Fig 9. The interface for PET state

- CAN STATE (figure 10)//2 (Compactor plate moves to the left for compacting a can). This is similar with the PET sate the difference being given by the PID parameters which are adapted for compressing a can.

Fig 10. The interface for CAN state

- TETRAPACK_STATE (Figure 11)// 3 (Compactor plate moves to the right for compacting a tetra pack). This is similar with the PET state the difference being given by the PID parameters which are adapted for compressing a can.

Fig 11. The interface for TETRAPACK state

- HOLD STATE //4 (Hold a specific time the compactor plate is the position). When limit switch will be activated the active plate will stop and will remain hold in position for a defined time (1500ms).
- PREHOME_STATE (Figure 12) // 5 (Positioning to the neutral position -reference). In this state the active plate is start moving from current position to the home position (baseline) using dedicated home speed parameters.

Fig 12. The interface for PREHOME state

- HOMING_STATE (Figure 13) // 6 (Compactor plate is in the neutral position waiting for a new compacting state). This is the state when the active plate is hold in home position waiting to start a new cycle. In this state the user can set parameters and insert a new waste in compactor.

Fig 13. The interface for HOMING state

- OFF_STATE // 7 (System is freezing). This case freezes the compactor when an error occur or the E-STOP is activated. Is the safe mode state if anything happen and the user want to stop any activity.

Smart Waste Management and Execution Application was developed as a Virtual Instrument in the graphical programming environment LabView (Savu 2014). The virtual instrument is capable to integrate all roles and capabilities assumed for level 4 at the operational level from the pyramid with Waste Management Architecture presented in figure 5. This software application communicates and exchange data with the controller from level 2 integrating the level 3 represented by SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) (Abaza, 2014). A sample from the data flow programming code is presented in the Virtual Instrument Diagram (Spanu, 2018) from the figure 14.

Fig 14. Sample of Virtual Instrument Diagram for Smart Waste Management and Execution Application

Statistics and data management is another section belonging to the Smart Waste Management and Execution Application. A sample of this is presented in the figure 15.

Fig 15. The interface for Statistics

Actual version integrates basic functionalities for managing the loading status of the selective waste bins and can alert when the bin is almost full, and this can be empty. This functionality could be improved by integrating it in the whole process of monitoring a cluster of several compactors and to take operation decisions for collecting the compacted waste in an optimized way.

Based on logging and data exchange from all subordinate levels the system become capable to collect data from the sensors and states machines modes and more than that. This open another direction of development which is related to designing new graphical and data analysis tools relevant for the operational level.

Prototype tests

Smart Waste Management and Execution Application presented in previous chapter was developed during the tests prototyping phase. According with the macroplanning the prototyping phase aims to reproduce and test the main function: reducing the waste volume. Another CAD version of the compactor was generated based on the materials and parts availability. In the Figure 16 is presented the CAD concept and the prototype made based on it.

Fig16. CAD concept (Sevastian, 2019)

The prototype tests were aimed at assessing the behaviour of the comparator using all types of waste (figure 17). It has proven to be functional, successfully performing the functions for which it was designed. At the end of the test process, good behaviour in terms of noise and vibration during operation was observed, without the need for further improvements in this direction. In addition, several things have been identified that can be improved.

Fig 17. Tests for different type of waste

Table 2 shows, by comparison, the initial dimensions with the dimensions of the compacted waste obtained from the testing of the prototype and using several types of waste.

Table 2. Dimensions of products

Waste Type	Material	Dimensions Initial [mm]	Dimensions after compacting [mm]	Compression ratio
Can 1	Metal	113	40	2.83:1
Beer Can	Metal	166	45	3.69:1
Can 2	Metal	131	40	3.28:1
Tetra Pack	Carton	202	40	5.05:1
PET 2l	Plastic	350	85	4.12:1
PET 1 0,5l	Plastic	187	65	2.87:1
PET 2 0,5l	Plastic	213	60	3.55:1

Product optimization analysis

According to the macroplanning the activity for product optimization analysis was performed during the prototyping process. It was used the method FMECA (Failure Modes, Effects and Criticality Analysis). The results of this analysis conducted to further development directions for the next

version of the compactor and Smart Waste Management and Execution Application. Here are some relevant aspects:

- Reducing the section of the active pressure plate by using another nut with a larger flange diameter improving the position of stress concentrations and reducing stress in the holes areas. No residual deformations were found in the pressure plate, but at high stress it was elastically deformed.
- The possibility to reduce the section of the marginal plates. No deformations were found during the tests.
- Resizing the guide rods. Elastic buckling was found under conditions of maximum effort.
- Improving solution for evacuating air from waste during compression.
- Improving solution to protect the area where the lead screw is located from the pressing area.
- Modification in the architecture of the structure so that its stroke is not obstructed by the bearings and their fasteners.
- Improve PID adaptive optimization by extending the trials on different types of waste.
- Improve the customization and sensing for Controller State Machines. New interfaces can be developed for customization of PID and configuration parameters.
- Improve the usability of interfaces from Front Panel for the virtual instrument developed in LabView.
- Extend and improve tests of communication module. Testing them in different scenarios.
- Extend the cloud computing and analysis capabilities

The current chosen solution for compactor and Smart Management Application has gone through multiple design phases, while having continuous improvements made based on performed analysis and performance criteria, eventually ending up with the building and testing of a functional prototype.

Conclusion

This paper presented an educational development model of a Waste Management System. Based on a well-defined macroplanning different teams proposes concepts designs and technical solutions for waste compactors. Based on these a Smart Waste Management Application was developed synchronized with the same macroplanning.

The innovative system was developed based on Industry 4.0 concepts and principles.

Experimental research for prototype design has highlighted the forces needed for efficient compaction of different types of recyclable materials.

Based on the experimentally determined forces, the main mechanical and software components of the system were designed and optimized.

Smart Waste Management and Execution Application was developed as a Virtual Instrument based on Waste Management Architecture with a customised Electrical System Architecture and Programming Controller State Machines. The virtual instrument is capable to integrate all roles and capabilities from automation pyramid assumed for level 4 at the operational level. This software application communicates and exchange data with the controller from level 2 integrating the level 3 represented by SCADA.

Based on product optimization analysis performed during the prototyping process the actual version of Smart Waste Management Application integrates also basic functionalities for managing the loading status of the selective waste bins and can alert when the bin is almost full, and this can be empty. This functionality could be improved by integrating it in the whole process of monitoring a cluster of several compactors and to take operation decisions for collecting the compacted waste in an optimized way.

Based on logging and data exchange from all subordinate levels the system become capable to collects data from the sensors and states machines modes and more than that. This open another direction of development which is related to designing new graphical and data analysis tools relevant for the operational level.

This paper proved that iterative product development using Project-Based Pedagogy (PBP) synchronised with vertical integration approach from Industry 4.0 can become a new integrative education model for developing technical and transversal competences in engineering.

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References

Abaza, B., Paraschiv, I., Spiroiu, M., Stanciu, C., (2015), Project-based pedagogy for a new product development, 9th International Technology, Education And Development Conference, INTED 2015, 2-4th March 2015, Madrid, Spain, ISBN: 978-84-606-5763-7, ISSN 2340-1079, Published by IATED Academy, Spain 2015, pag 4348-4359.

Abaza, B., Savu, T., Spânu, P., (2014), Îndrumar de laborator - Algoritmi, Editura Printech,

Aazam, Mohammad & St-Hilaire, Marc & Lung, Chung-Horng & Lambadaris, Ioannis. (2016). Cloud-based smart waste management for smart cities. 188-193. 10.1109/CAMAD.2016.7790356.

Hisham Che Soh, Z., Azeer Al-Hami Husa, M., Afzal Che Abdullah, S, and Affandi Shafie, M., "Smart Waste Collection Monitoring and Alert System via IoT," 2019 IEEE 9th Symposium on Computer Applications & Industrial Electronics (ISCAIE), Malaysia, 2019, pp. 50-54, doi: 10.1109/ISCAIE.2019.8743746.

Savu, T., Abaza, B., Spanu, P., (2014), Îndrumar de laborator – Reprezentări Grafice, Editura Printech.

Savu, T., Szuder, A., Arsenoiu, L., (1999), Bazele programării în LabVIEW, Editura Printech.,

Savu, T., Grigorescu, G., Neacșu, I., Garabet, E., (2006), Bazele instrumentației virtuale LabVIEW, Editura Atelier Didactic.

Sevastian, M., Cerbu, R., Drăgan, I., (2019), Studii privind dezvoltarea unui produs de compactat deșeuri reciclabile. Pag. 65-70, Revista de Inginerie Industrială, Nr. 4, ISSN 2601-7938.

Spanu, P., Savu, T., Abaza, B., (2018), Îndrumar de laborator bilingv (Român – Englez) Programarea Calculatoarelor, Editura PRINTECH.